

Concepts Distorted by Ideologies

A View on Medieval
“Romanian” Art (1945–1989)*

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Abstract – Concepts Distorted by Ideologies. A View on Medieval “Romanian” Art (1945–1989) – The role of medieval art in national-identity discourse has received too little attention in the historiography of Romania’s totalitarian regime of 1945 to 1989. Analyzing the concept of “Romanian art”, this paper reveals traces of medieval art history under Soviet ideological pressure and opens the way to further investigation. The article explores the concept used mainly by other authors, including work disseminated by national-scale publishing houses throughout the Communist period and its aftermath. The process uncovers certain efforts to impose the term “Romanian medieval art” on the entire territory of Romania, especially around 1965.

Works using the concept “Romanian art” emerge chronologically in their political context, and they include official attitudes and theses related to the culture and historical writing. In addition, documents from a private archive function in the analysis. This way the diverse contributions of some medieval art historians to propagate the historical myths serving the regime’s propaganda – such as the myth of the unity of Romanians –, as well as some critical attitudes towards parts of the national ideology become more readily apparent.

Keywords

Romanian Communism, national identity, historical myths, medieval art historiography

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A quarter of a century after the fall of Communism, Romanian art historiography still includes only a few critical evaluations of its relation with totalitarian ideology. Historians and archaeologists of different generations, having been influenced by the literature of dissent and by intellectuals from other fields, began these evaluations immediately after the fall of the regime in December 1989. They examined Protochronism, the different forms of intellectual oppression, collaborationism, as well as outright silence or taking refuge in positivist approaches¹. Regarding the historiography of medieval art, which this paper

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¹ See for example: Radu Popa, “Arheologia română sub presiune. Activiști și securiști în templul lui Clio” [Romanian Archaeology under Pressure. Activists and Securitate Members in the Temple of Clio], *Revista* 22, 1/2–3 (1990); Șerban Papacostea, “Captive Clio. Romanian Historiography under Communist Rule”, *European History Quarterly*, xxvi (1996), pp. 181–208; Lucian Boia, *Istorie și mit în conștiința românească* [History and Myth in the Romanian Consciousness], Bucharest 1997; Alexandru Zub, *Orizont închis. Istoriografia română sub comunism* [Closed Horizon. Romanian Historiography during Communism], Iași 2000; Andi Mihalache, *Istorie și practici discursive în România „democrat-populară”* [History Discourse Practices in “Popular Democratic” Romania], Bucharest 2003; Radu-Alexandru Dragoman, Sorin Oanță-Marghitu, *Arheologie și politică în România* [Archaeology and Politics in Romania], Baia Mare 2013. Some of these publications have also been edited abroad.

1/ Former Cistercian abbey Cârța (Kerz, Kerc), Sibiu County, Transylvania, 13th–14th centuries

focuses on, the tendency was rather to commend, reedit and reiterate their predecessors' theses, especially those of the two figures dominating the scene at different times, Virgil Vătășianu (1902–1993) and Vasile Drăguț (1928–1987), as well as the theses of their disciples. Their qualities and sacrifices had been emphasized, together with their authority in the field, but with no mention of their inevitable concessions with imposed research approaches, clichés and distortions in views and language, and their voluntary and involuntary contributions to the myths promoted by Communism and by the identity discourse

of the time². This attitude was caused by a lack of appetite for theoretical debates, by a major attachment to the past and by positivist approaches. Until now, analyses has focused on the art history prior to 1945, while analyses regarding the Communist period (whether concretely or just tangentially) are mere exceptions³.

After more than a quarter of a century of research on the cultural policy in Communist Romania, the general frame necessary for intellectual activity has been relatively well defined. For the greater part of the twentieth century, de-Stalinization focused on the concept of the nation, the

humanities were called to contribute to the image of an authentic and valuable Romania in relation to the world. Under ideological pressure, history and the subjects believed to be its “auxiliaries” (including art history) contributed to this image to different extents. The degree and means of their input must still be analyzed in a wider context, in order to achieve a more nuanced picture of the historiographical landscape.

The present paper analyses the concept of “Romanian art” associated with medieval art and architecture and the phrases it related to in both scholarly and wider-access (popularizing) science literature from 1945 until today. For this purpose, a list of publications' content (of certain syntheses, monographs and other studies) was examined in relation to prefaces, introductions and chapters with explicit programmatic value, therefore aiming to legitimize and consecrate the authors and their theses.

Even today, the concepts under scrutiny are quite common both in scholarly and popular literature published after 1989, in syllabi and in university courses, in conference papers, in the names of art galleries and in their catalogues – despite the fact that they also tend to include the art of the ethnic groups and encompass extensive periods of time. Such standardizing concepts are now part of the common vocabulary⁴, but they can also generate some confusion. Printed on the cover of certain books, without any description, they can transmit the fact that the subject is Romania, but the contents of the books, the time periods and the regions they address are all unclear – especially if the reader knows that Romania is a state whose borders fluctuated up until 1947, it was compiled of many historical provinces that are ethnically, religiously, culturally and artistically diverse, with rich and complicated backgrounds, dating from prehistory to modernity, until they were politically unified.

I will focus on establishing how old this ethnocentric tendency is – the tendency to enclose all artistic manifestations from historical Romanian provinces into “Romanian art” or “Romanian architecture” – by analyzing the way in which the provinces are presented in the most important syntheses published in the Communist period,

and what the historical contexts of these provinces were. The fact that the aforementioned phrases appeared on the covers of certain books long before the Union of 1918 is easily noticeable, but only in the case of certain regions, or only in the case of Romanian art and architecture from Transylvania. They are, of course, also found during the interwar period, which was dominated by an obsession with the search for national identity in different cultural fields⁵. Regarding these years, I must mention two publications: *Histoire de l'Art roumain ancien* by Nicolae Iorga and Gheorghe Balș (Paris 1922)⁶, and *Istoria arhitecturii românești din cele mai vechi timpuri până la 1900* [The History

2 Lucian Boia mentions some of the more popular opinions amongst historians, namely that “writing about communism is not good” because “we lack information” and “we do not have the necessary perspective, we run the risk of being subjective”. Boia, *Istorie și mit* (n. 1), pp. 376–377. As well, the reluctance may be connected to the idea that some viewpoints can come across as impious towards important figures (some of whom still active), and to the fact that investigations are difficult, they require a critical approach to the testimonies and a use of historical methods (including the methodology of oral history), together with access to the public and private archives, most of which are not inventoried.

3 For example, Corina Simion, *Artă și identitate națională în opera lui Virgil Vătășianu* [Art and National Identity in the Work of Virgil Vătășianu], Cluj-Napoca 2002; Alice Mocănescu, “National Art as Legitimate Art: ‘National’ between Tradition and Ideology in Ceausescu’s Romania” in *The Contours of Legitimacy in Central Europe. New Approaches in Graduate Studies*, conference proceedings (European Studies Centre, St Antony’s College Oxford, 24–26 May 2002), available online [http://euroacademia.eu/conference/6th-re-inventing-eastern-europe, last accessed on 25. 08. 2016]; Ana Maria Gruia, “Virgil Vatasianu (1902–1993)”, in *Rewriting the Middle Ages in the twentieth century. 2: National traditions*, Jaume Aurell Cardona, Julia Pavón Benito eds, Turnhout 2009, pp. 207–223; Corina Teacă, “In Search of National Traditions: Art History in Romania”, in *Art History and Visual Studies in Europe. Transnational Discourses and National Frameworks*, Matthew Rampley et al. eds, Leiden/Boston 2012. On the necessity of more detailed analyses of the discourses on art history and on its participation in the national project of the Communist era, see for example: Matthew Rampley, “Art historians in Romania”, review of Vlad Țoca, *Art Historical Discourse in Romania, Budapest 2011*, in *Journal of Art Historiography*, XIII (2015), pp. 1–3.

4 A radical, discrepant note is made by Augustin Ioan in his lectures and texts that often contain the assertion: “Romanian architecture does not exist”. The architect disputes earlier historiography and the identity paradigms that had been transferred from nationalist policies and he wishes to point out the fact that the Romanians have had regional styles instead of a “national style”. For example, see Augustin Ioan, “Nu există arhitectură „românească”!” [Romanian Architecture Does Not Exist!], *Observatorul cultural*, 10. 03. 2005, available online [http://www.observatorcultural.ro/articol/nu-exista-arhitectura-romaneasca-2, last accessed on 20. 09. 2016].

5 Irina Livezeanu, *Cultural Politics in Greater Romania. Regionalism, National Building and Ethnic Struggle 1918–1930*, Ithaca 1995, pp. 211–244; Boia, *Istorie și mit* (n. 1), p. 243; Ruxandra Demetrescu, “The Concept of National Style in Artistic Historiography: Asserting a Critical Vocabulary”, in *Key Concepts of Romanian History: Alternative Approaches to Socio-Political Languages*, Victor Neumann, Armin Heinen eds, Budapest 2013, pp. 315–332.

6 The publication does not include Transylvania. It was probably conceived earlier, before the Union in 1918 (Vlad Țoca, *Art Historical Discourse in Romania*, Budapest 2011, p. 18).

2/ Fortified Lutheran parish church in Biertan (Birihalm, Berehalom), formerly Catholic church dedicated to the Virgin Mary, Sibiu County, Transylvania, 15th–16th centuries

of Romanian Architecture from Time Immemorial until 1900] by Grigore Ionescu⁷, although both of them only covered Wallachia and the Moldavian region.

In the context of the Second World War and the Communist takeover, the national discourse was fractured in the period of time that followed. Before the 1946 elections, Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej, secretary general of the Romanian Workers' Party (RWP) announced that his program did not represent "a solution of continuity with cultural traditions". A year later, the newly installed regime launched the project of an essentially Marxist "cultural revolution". Although the concept of "national culture" was still valid, in reality a brutal and rapid Sovietisation was taking

place. The education reform introduced in 1948 sought a transformation into a mass education system based on the Soviet model that was propagandistic, antireligious and introduced new courses: the Russian language and Marxism-Leninism. Grammar, history and philosophy textbooks were then rewritten according to a Marxist-Leninist scheme, the teachers' contracts were suspended and the Academy (which mostly opposed the new power) and the centralized research institutes were restructured. The historians and archaeologists were given new research tasks regarding the Slavs and Byzantium. This new way of approaching history was established by Mihail Roller, a representative of the ruling party, who was in charge of the academic world⁸. In 1947,

several art historians were removed, including I. D. Ștefănescu⁹. George Oprescu was at first sent into retirement, but was later reintegrated into the Academy and charged with new tasks¹⁰, and the name Nicolae Iorga (a prominent cultural figure, author of numerous studies, including in art history, but also a politician, assassinated in 1940) could only be uttered in negative terms, having

the ruling political power wished to control all church institutions, see: I. D. Ștefănescu. 1886–1981, Alexandru Zub, Flavius Solomon eds. Iași 1997; Țoca, *Art Historical Discourse* (n.6), pp. 32–36.

10 George Oprescu (1881–1969) is also known as a historian, art critic, diplomat and collector. His relationship with the ruling power after 1945 and his scholarly activity have not been sufficiently studied. Between 1923 and 1930 he was the secretary of the League of Nations Committee on Intellectual Cooperation. He taught art history at the University of Bucharest (1931) until its disbandment through the reform in 1948, after which he worked at the institutes of archives or of fine arts. He was the director of the Institute of Art History in Bucharest between 1948 and 1969. From 1938 he became an associate and later an honorary tenured member of the Academy that was restructured by the Communist regime. His career began by studying folk art, but continued on several different fields, from medieval architecture, to graphic arts, painting, and modern sculpture. *Enciclopedia istoriografiei românești* [Encyclopaedia of Romanian Historiography], Bucharest 1978, pp. 245–246; Țoca, *Art Historical Discourse* (n. 6), pp. 100 ff.; Alin Ciupală, "Testamentul academicianului George Oprescu, întemeietorul Institutului de Istoria Artei al Academiei Române" [The Testament of the Academic George Oprescu, Founder of the Institute of Art History of the Romanian Academy], *Studii și Cercetări de Istoria artei. Artă Plastică*, IV (48), 2014, pp. 153–158.

3/ Interior of the fortified Lutheran church in Prejmer (Tartlau), formerly Catholic church dedicated to Holy Cross, Brașov County, Transylvania, 13th century

been considered a representative of bourgeois historiography¹¹. Because he had written that artistic evolution could be made through religious art, in 1950, Virgil Vătășianu, the art historian from Cluj, was demoted from professor to associate professor, after which his position in the university was dissolved in 1952¹². The ruling party resorted to identifying and destroying publications deemed incompatible with the new project and elaborated an official history handbook, the only official handbook published by the state, in order to both purify and unify the discourse. Furthermore, it established new institutes of influence and control, besides the party schools, in order to form activists and a new elite. Control was exerted through censorship institutions that were equipped with new practical mechanisms. In 1949, following the model offered by the Soviet *Glavlit*, the institution that would go on to have the most censorship activity until 1977 was established, namely the General Directorate of Press and Printing (GDPP), ancillary to the Directorate of Propaganda, besides the Council of Ministers of the Romanian People's Republic (RPR)¹³. Censorship and self-censorship were meant to regulate academic conduct¹⁴ and approvals for publication financing were actually obtained from the Secretariat of the Central Committee of the RPR¹⁵. Historians who have analyzed the historical writings from the 1950s consider that those years must have been the hardest in Romania after the war¹⁶.

In the second half of the decade, after Stalin's death in 1953, Roller's power diminished and a certain distancing from the Kremlin ensued, especially after the withdrawal of Soviet troops from Romania in 1958. Having been allowed by the authorities, especially after 1955, national figures began to re-enter the historical discourse¹⁷. The ruling authorities opened up new opportunities in the academic field, by establishing new institutions or by reorganizing the old ones, through new staffing or by reinstating the previously deposed specialists, and by establishing periodical publications. A wide-ranging plan was announced in 1955 by the Congress of the Romanian Workers' Party, alongside a statement for the need to compile an academic work on the general history of Romania (which would be published in three volumes, in

1960, 1962 and 1964). This was followed by embedding certain syntheses on the Romanian language, on science, architecture, fine arts, theatre, as well as dictionaries and other tools, into the research projects of the departments of the Academy and of the universities¹⁸. This is the historical context in which the collective work called *Scurtă istorie a artelor plastice în R.P.R.* [Short History of the Fine Arts in R.P.R.]¹⁹ was printed by the Publishing House of the Academy under the coordination of George Oprescu. The first volume was dedicated to medieval art: *Arta românească din epoca feudală* [Romanian Art in the Feudal Period]²⁰. The work did not achieve what its title anticipated. In that period, historians of art and architecture did not have access to enough systematic research to build a summary of the major art and architecture manifestations across the country. The greatest omission was Transylvania, and the rectification of this omission in the following publication on medieval art contributed to the significant impact of the latter work.

After a rather long period of respite, a thousand-page manuscript (written between 1936 and 1956) turned into the first volume of Virgil Vătășianu's work in 1959, *Istoria artei feudale din Țările Române. Arta în perioada de dezvoltare a feudalismului*²¹ [The History of Feudal Art in the Romanian Principalities. Art in the Period of Feudal Development]. The author had been given the right to resume teaching his art history courses at the University in Cluj only one year before. He had acquired the education of a European intellectual²², and was receptive to the methodological suggestions of the Viennese school and foreign literature. Having had a keen critical vein, he was also aware of the value of information offered by archaeology (which medieval art and architecture across Romania depended on), conducting his own field research and absorbing much of the historiography on the art of the ethnic minorities (Hungarian, German, etc.), while distancing himself from certain theses in Hungarian historiography. Vătășianu thus offered the first volume of a monumental work, structured in large chapters that respected the particularities of each historical province. Chronologically, he discussed the art of the eleventh to the sixteenth

centuries (until 1562), and the following period was to be included in a second volume, which he never published²³. The author's interest in Romanian medieval art developed early, ever since he noticed that there was a history of every people, including the ones from the Balkans, but the Romanians were not mentioned anywhere²⁴.

Vătășianu's volume was delivered to the publishing house of the Academy and the author was reinstated at the university in a period of a clear ideological relaxation²⁵. Shortly after, manifestations appeared with new efforts to resume the "fight against bourgeois ideology":

4/ Orthodox church dedicated to St Nicholas in Bălinești, Suceava County, Moldavia, 1494–1499

11 Zub, *Orizont* (n. 1), pp. 36 ff.

12 "Pentru o istorie a artei românești. Convorbire cu academicianul Virgil Vătășianu cu prilejul împlinirii vârstei de 90 de ani. Interviu realizat de Virgil Pop" [For a History of Romanian Art. Discussions with Academic Virgil Vătășianu on his 90th Birthday. Interview by Virgil Pop], *Buletinul Comisiei Monumentelor Istorice*, 1 (1992), p. 85.

13 Liliana Corobca, *Controlul cărții: cenzura literaturii în regimul comunist din România* [Book Audit: the Censoring Literature during the Communist Regime in Romania], Iași 2014, pp. 14 ff.; Ion Zănea, "Direcția Generală pentru Presă și Tipărituri. Comitetul pentru Presă și Tipărituri – instituția de cenzură/pază a regimului comunist" [The General Administrations of Press and Publications. The Committee of Press and Publication – the Censorship/Security of the Communist Regime], in *Stalinizare și Destalinizare. Evoluții instituționale și impact social* [Stalinization and De-Stalinization. Institutional Evolutions and Social Impact], Cosmin Budeancă, Florentin Olteanu eds, Iași 2016, pp. 157–170.

14 In 1949, during a meeting, the president of the new Academy stated: "In our socialist-democratic regime and in the socialist society we are building, freedom of opinion is an active freedom, a freedom that is monitored and disciplined through itself in relation with the working class and its ideology". Mihalache, *Istorie* (n. 1), p. 75.

15 *Ibidem*, p. 76. Bureaucracy in culture actually consisted of numerous committees, directorates, services, councils and boards that were part of the general central structure of the state and carried out the orders of the party under the oversight of the ideology activists of the Department for Agitation and Propaganda of the RPR Central Committee.

16 For an overview of the period, see Zub, *Orizont* (n. 1), pp. 36–71; Gabriel Moisa, *Istorie și propagandă istorică în România. 1945–1989* [History and Historical Propaganda in Romania. 1945–1989], Oradea 2002, pp. 32–44; Mihalache, *Istorie* (n. 1), pp. 113–183.

17 Moisa, *Istorie* (n. 16), pp. 53–54.

18 Pavel Țugui, *Istoria și limba română în vremea lui Gheorghiu-Dej. Memoriile unui fost șef de Secție a CC al PMR* [History and the Romanian Language under Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej. Memoirs of a Former Head of Department of CC of RPR], Bucharest 1999, pp. 36, 54 ff.

19 The title included the phrase "Romanian People's Republic", just like the *Istoria R.P.R.* [The History of the R.P.R.] edited by Mihail Roller (Bucharest 1956). In other case, e.g. *Istoria României* (1960–1964) [The History of Romania (1960–1964)], historians involved in the writing of the treatise managed to avoid such a title after a series of disputes. Țugui, *Istoria* (n. 18), pp. 34–360.

20 The work was published in two volumes, in 1957 and in 1958. The first exploited the arts from until the eighteenth century and the second treated the nineteenth century.

21 The ways in which art historians used certain concepts and theoretical models, namely "feudalism" in this case, certainly derive from those of the Romanian historians and would benefit from a separate analysis. For an analysis of the terms "feudalism" and "feudal", see Cosmin Popa-Gorjanu, "Feudalismul românesc" [Romanian feudalism], *Mediævalia Transilvanica*, VII–VIII/1–2 (2003–2004), pp. 39–51.

22 Vătășianu studied in Cluj, Prague and Vienna. Beginning with 1931, he was (with intermissions) the secretary of the Romanian School in Rome. He returned to Romania and, beginning with 1947, he held a teaching position at art history department of the university in Cluj. Furthermore, he was in charge of the Department of Art History of the Academy in Cluj, having to collaborate with George Oprescu in Bucharest by participating in the official research planning at the Academy. He authored an impressive number of works that particularly approached medieval art history and participated in numerous conferences in Romania and abroad. Through his teaching position and through the position held at the Academy, he established new ways of approaching the arts of different epochs, especially from Transylvania. His publications and visibility abroad brought his great prestige in Romania and he was awarded different honours, including from the Romanian state. Mircea Țoca, "Bibliografia academicianului Virgil Vătășianu" [The Bibliography of the Academic Virgil Vătășianu], *Ars Transilvanica*, IV (1994), pp. 9–14; "Pentru o istorie" (n. 12), pp. 83–86; Gruia, "Virgil Vătășianu" (n. 3), pp. 207–223; Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 17–22, 74 ff.

23 In the research plans of the Academy, the introduction of the second volume had been repeatedly postponed on the grounds of its overlap with other subjects under development, according to Vătășianu's testimonies on which his monograph was based. Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 106–109. Later, the author himself changed the plans by including different chapters of medieval and pre-modern art history in the treatise *Istoria României* (vols II–III, 1962, 1964), in the volume *Istoria artelor plastice*, I–II, 1968–1970 edited by George Oprescu, or even by approaching other subjects, including ones of European art.

24 "Pentru o istorie" (n. 12), p. 83; Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 25–26, 100–101.

25 At that time, the author was considered to be non-political, a cosmopolitan, suspected of deviation, of having "unhealthy" origins for being part of the middle class. Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), p. 108. On the one hand, the book was highly appreciated, as most reviews show. See e.g. Mircea Țoca, "Virgil Vătășianu – savantul umanist, creator de școală" [Virgil Vătășianu – Humanist Scholar, Creator of Schools], in *Studii de istoria artei* [Studies of Art History], *Idem* ed., Cluj-Napoca 1982. An exception seems to be Emil Lăzărescu's critical review (*Studii și Cercetări de Istoria Artei* [Studies and Researches of Art History], II [1959], pp. 286–308). Besides the strictly scientific objections, the reviewer also brought accusations regarding the author's insufficient adherence to the ideology, as was requested in 1948 and the absence of a Marxist interpretation of the evolution of religious ideas. Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 100–105.

5/ Vaulting of the south porch, church of Bălinești, end of the 15th century

the re-communist “cultural deviations” and the “retrograde concepts” of which intellectuals were accused reappeared, along with accusations of being against socialism and against “the working classes”²⁶. After certain evaluations, many of the

“cultural guidance” objectives from previous years seemed not to have been met. In that context, in December 1960, an order was issued to the Art Department of the Academy, which declared the need for research to commence in different fields

of study: Romanian art history, Romanian music history, etc.²⁷ Therefore, the research plans of the art historians employed by the Academy had been changed. Art historical treatises on which they had been working for many years were then remodeled in accordance with the new guidelines. The structure and problems of content were discussed in numerous meetings in Bucharest, held by the group of collaborators including art historians, historians and archaeologists and in which Virgil Vătășianu was also co-opted from the Cluj branch of the Academy. Initially, Oprescu and Vătășianu were to edit the treatise together, but, because of their differences in opinion, the latter simply remained an author of the chapters dedicated to Transylvania. Letters from the personal archive of Vătășianu sent to Oprescu in 1962 and a stenograph from the meeting of the scientific council of the Institute of Art History show the ways in which they worked on the new treatise. The members of that diverse group, having had different formations and views, tried to find the means through which Romanian originality in “medieval art” and “the role played by the masses in the making of history” could be brought to light. They tried to assert the remarkable age of folk art in relation to high art, to show that folk art had “millennial” origins, to present the evolution of artistic phenomena and to put emphasis on elements that showed a unity between the historical provinces of the country. The latter issue seemed more difficult to solve, with the discussions on this topic usually reaching the conclusion that “no matter how numerous the elements of unity were between the provinces, from an artistic viewpoint the elements that differentiated them were even greater, which means that an argument based on general historical facts, on facts provided by the artistic history of these differences would implicitly be much richer than that of unity” (Emil Lăzărescu)²⁸. In the end, after

²⁶ Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 82–83.

²⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 145.

²⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 147–184, with the original text. Furthermore, the observation made by the historian Mihail Berza during the same meeting: “We must include a division into periods, which I truly believe to be faulty, but one that is meant to enclose the three countries, including Transylvania with its existing disparities and an explanation for these disparities. They must show unity, since we have included them in a book. The connection between the three Romanian regions must be explained, for they are present in the book but are not sufficiently interlaced”.

6/ Greek-Catholic church in Șurdești, Maramureș County, dedicated to Archangels Michael and Gabriel, 18th century

7/ Portal from the church in Brădet, Bihor County, Crișana, 18th century

8/ Orthodox parish church in Densuș,
Hunedoara County, Transylvania, 13th century

9/ Orthodox Monastery of Cozia, Vâlcea
County, Wallachia, 14th century

many years, between 1968 and 1970, the treatise was published in only two volumes (out of the five volumes initially planned), with the title *Istoria artelor plastice din România* [The History of Fine Arts in Romania], which presented art in the period prior to the nineteenth century. The first volume included an anonymous introduction (a common practice at that time in the case of collective works) and a chapter on folk art (Paul Petrescu) which was considered to be the oldest and most representative art for Romanians, although the chapter presented monuments that dated only from the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries²⁹. Three long chapters followed and were chronologically divided; the first chapter began with prehistoric art and ended with the fourteenth century [“Art in Romania from

Time Immemorial to the First Decades of the Fourteenth Century”]; the subchapters were structured according to each historical province.

Grigore Ionescu’s *Istoria arhitecturii în România* [The History of Romanian Architecture] is also part of the wave of syntheses required from specialists and was published in two volumes, the first in 1963 and the second in 1965³⁰. The author thus revisited one of his older subjects from the interwar period, but he worked consistently and he partially changed its title, as he would do again for a new edition in 1981.

Somewhat at the same time as the *Istoria artelor plastice din România*, a different group of contributors consisting of Vasile Drăguț³¹ together with art critics and literary historians (Vasile Florea,

Dan Grigorescu, Marin Mihalache) was working on *Pictura românească în imagini. 1111 reproduceri* [Romanian Painting in Images. 1111 Reproductions], a popularizing work first published in 1970 by the Meridiane publishing house in several

researcher at the Institute for Art History in Bucharest, which was subordinated to the Academy. In 1964 he became an associate professor, and in 1971 a university professor at the Institute of Fine Arts, of which he also became chancellor between 1971 and 1976. He was the director of the Directorate of Museums (1968–1971), of the Directorate of Artistic and Historic Monuments (1968–1971) and of the Directorate of National Cultural Heritage (1971–1976). He was also a member of the ICOM, ICOMOS and ICCROM. In 1969, he became a member of the Romanian Communist Party. His bibliography includes both scholarly works (mostly on the subject of medieval art) and conferences and wide access works about historical monuments, in which field he had presented great contributions (both scholarly and administrative). Furthermore, he was a member and leader of multiple editorial offices and publishing houses, like Meridiane (where he published several books) and Editura Politică [Political Publishing House]. Iozeana Postăvaru, *Vasile Drăguț. Repere biografice. Opera* [Vasile Drăguț. Bibliographic References and Opus], *Buletinul Comisiunii Monumentelor Istorice*, XII–XVI/1 (2001–2005), pp. 168–190; Tereza Sinigalia, “Unitate și continuitate în Arta Românească. 70 de ani de la nașterea profesorului Vasile Drăguț (1927–1987)” [Unity and Continuity in Romanian Art. 70 Years after the Birth of Professor Vasile Drăguț (1927–1987)], *Ars Transsylvanica*, VIII–IX (1998–1999), pp. 5–16.

²⁹ A similar organizing structure of studies, in which folk art was the primary subject, can also be found in the first issues of the Institute’s journal, *Studii și Cercetări de Istoria Artei*, which debuted in 1954. Furthermore, the great importance folk art is also visible in the researchers’ annual reports published in the journal.

³⁰ The first was titled “De la orânduirea comunei primitive până la sfârșitul veacului al XVI-lea” [From the Social Structure of the Village to the End of the 16th Century], and the second “De la sfârșitul veacului al XVI-lea până la începutul celui de al cincilea deceniu al veacului al XX-lea” [From the End of the 16th Century until the Beginning of the Fifth Decade of the 20th Century].

³¹ Vasile Drăguț studied at the Institute for Fine Arts in Bucharest, after which he held two temporary positions at the Museum of Art and at the Department of Fine Arts. He was dismissed from the latter on ideological grounds. From 1961 he has worked as a

10/ Interior of the Lutheran parish church in Mediaș (Mediasch, Medgyes), formerly Catholic church dedicated to St Margaret with an altarpiece, Sibiu County, Transylvania, 14th–15th centuries

languages: Romanian, French, English, German and Russian. From a posthumous point of view, this volume represented a turning point for Drăguț, for he had first tried to include the images known from archaeological discoveries (Cucuteni pottery, for example) together with the ones dated before 1800 as a “phenomenon that shows unity in the Romanian territories, since the evolution of the components was exclusively chronological and stylistic”³². But, as it was later revealed, this model had already existed and this concept frequently appeared in his works after 1965³³.

After more than a decade of fieldwork, Drăguț published an encyclopedic dictionary of “Romanian medieval art”³⁴, the only dictionary of its kind up to nowadays. It contains both terms from the fields of art and architecture, and a list of monuments ordered according to their localities from around the year 1000 until the beginning of the nineteenth century, that is, what the author regarded as “old Romanian art”³⁵. The author used this expression, despite the risk of overlapping with the art of antiquity, on which the *Dicționarul enciclopedic de artă veche a României* [The encyclopedic dictionary of old art in Romania] (1980)³⁶ was being prepared. He wrote in the foreword of his dictionary that medieval art, “through its entire evolution, could express the spiritual unity of our people, prefacing the political unity made at the end of an irreversible process”³⁷. Even in this instance, the contents (which are mostly descriptive) appear less affected by ideology than the clearly normative titles, introductions, and prefaces. Furthermore, Drăguț tried to construct the image of a Gothic style that had developed all throughout Romania³⁸, from the “early Gothic” in Transylvania, to the east, in the Moldavian region, and in the south, in Wallachia. He even revisited the late wooden architecture from The Land of Lapus and Maramures in Northern Romania [Figs 1–7]. There, during the Baroque period, “the creative boldness of artisans” was stimulated, calling them “the builders of those amazing wooden churches whose tall towers with elongated crests pierce the sky, like the beams of the great cathedrals once did”³⁹.

Despite the previously more or less ambitious collective publications, Vasile Drăguț still considered Vătășianu’s book to have been the most

important reference work in medieval art historiography. It would have provided “an open path towards the elaboration of ample treatise-like presentations”. Everything that had been published before would have been insufficient; it would not have had the characteristics of a general history of the arts. Therefore, the elaboration of an ample work in two volumes would be justified, a work which would approach art from prehistory to the contemporary times. The author surpassed his subject and wrote a second volume, entitled *Arta românească. I. Preistorie. Antichitate. Ev Mediu. Renaștere. Baroc* [Romanian Art. I. Prehistory. Antiquity. The Middle Ages. Renaissance. Baroque] (Meridiane, 1982). The second volume was edited

32 Sinigalia, “Unitate” (n. 31), p. 6.

33 In 1965, one of his courses was titled *Arta medievală pe teritoriul României* [Medieval Art in Romania] and, between 1971 and 1978, it was changed to *Arta veche românească. Tipologia artei românești vechi* [Romanian Medieval Art. The Typology of Romanian Medieval Art]. The titles of scientific or instructional conferences held at the Artists Union, at the Ștefan Gheorghiu University had also been changed during courses, in the magazines of that time (*Scânteia*, *Viața Românească*, *Contemporanul*) and in radio or television shows. Numerous studies and presentations of monuments or of issues regarding medieval art and titles that show the originality of Romanian medieval art and of other subjects typical to nationalist Communist propaganda: *Capacitatea de sinteză și originalitatea universală a artei vechi românești* [The Synthesis Ability and the Universal Originality of Romanian Medieval Art], *Fondul unitar al artei vechi românești* [The Unitary Collection of Romanian Medieval Art] etc. See the bibliography in Postăvaru, *Vasile Drăguț* (n. 31), pp. 168–190.

34 Vasile Drăguț, *Dicționarul enciclopedic de artă medievală românească* [The Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Medieval Art in Romania], Bucharest 1976.

35 Previously, in 1970, the series of articles on medieval art was published: *Pagini de veche artă românească* [Studies of Old Romanian Art], 1–v/1, Bucharest, which will have been published until its v/1 issue from 1985, after which it was discontinued.

36 Radu Florescu, Hadrian Daicovicu, Lucian Roșu, *Dicționar enciclopedic de artă veche a României* [The Encyclopedic Dictionary of Romanian Old Art], Bucharest 1980.

37 Drăguț, *Dicționar* (n. 34), p. 5.

38 Vasile Drăguț, *Arta gotică în România* [Gothic Art], Bucharest 1979.

39 *Ibidem*, p. 7. Regarding the title, the author states in the first pages that it could have been *Aventurile artei gotice în România* [The Adventures of Gothic Art in Romania]. This type of publication, in which the territorial borders had been stretched by style in order to show this development on the entire territory, was not singular in historiography and it was not a habit limited to one publishing house. For example, this also happened in the case of Gheorghe Sebestyén’s book, *O pagină din istoria arhitecturii din România. Renașterea* [Pages from the History of Architecture in Romania. Renaissance], Bucharest 1987, which approaches the subject of Transylvania; among its 200 pages, a chapter entitled “Arhitectura Renașterii în Moldova și Țara Românească. Unele concluzii” [Renaissance Architecture in the Moldavian Region and in Wallachia. Some Conclusions] occupied less than seven pages. This type of excess can also be found in the case of Nicolae Sabău, *Sculptura barocă în România* [Baroque Sculpture in Romania], Bucharest 1992, published by Meridiane publishing house. But this author revisited the subject in 2002 (*Metamorfoze ale barocului transilvan. Vol. 1. Sculptura* [Metamorphoses of the Transylvania Baroque. Volume 1. Sculpture]), at the Dacia publishing house in Cluj.

11/ Interior of the Orthodox church of St John the New in Suceava, Suceava County, Moldavia, 1522

12/ Wall painting inside of the formerly Catholic chapel of the church of Hărman (Honigberg, Szászhermány), Brașov County, Transylvania, 15th century

by Vasile Florea (art critic and historian, one of the contributors of the 1970 volume) and addressed modern and contemporary art. As the subtitle indicated, the structure of the first volume focused on the great historical epochs (from the Paleolithic until 1800). The chapter entitled *Arta medievală românească* [Romanian Medieval Art] was followed by *Arta românească între medieval și modern* [Romanian Art between the Middle Ages and the Modern Era] and the table of contents was divided into categories (architecture, sculpture, painting and other arts). The author stated that he was aware of what taking on such a risky endeavor implied. The foreword also contains a series of justifications regarding the structure and the “innovative approach”, invoking the cases of the Italians and the Germans, invoking Nicolae Iorga, the great advocate of “the unity of the Romanian people”, and also stating his own belief that “throughout history, the spiritual junctions in the three Romanian regions represented the factors of permanent emulation and unity”. Through the style of the presentation, “the accomplishments that gradually contributed to establishing the climate for national conscience, for the understanding of the spiritual values all Romanians have in common” were strongly asserted. Furthermore, the author tried to assure the reader of the fact that he did not neglect the artistic accomplishments of minority groups: the Hungarians, the Saxons and the Szeklers. On the contrary, “by assessing the artworks of our countrymen with sufficient appreciation”, the author affirms that he “tried to also focus on the constant internal artistic exchanges, which created a favorable context for the acclimatization of foreign stylistic trends that have gained an unmistakable mark of authority”⁴⁰.

Apparently, this way of viewing medieval art did not meet with much opposition in the publications that underwent censorship⁴¹. There were critical perspectives nonetheless, just that these

40 Vasile Drăguț, *Arta românească. I. Preistorie. Antichitate. Ev Mediu. Renaștere. Baroc*, Bucharest 1982, pp. 5–8.

41 A few of his remarks about the way in which Drăguț contrived the *Arta gotică* (n. 38), come to light in Virgil Vătășianu, “Considerații privind unele particularități regionale și trăsături naționale ale arhitecturii românești în epoca feudală” [Considerations Regarding Some Regional Particularities and National Features of the Romanian Architecture in the Feudal Epoch], in *Studii de artă veche românească și universală*, Bucharest 1987, p. 71.

13/ Archangel Michael, central panel of a triptych, Byzantine workshop, 15th century / National Museum of Art of Romania, Bucharest

could not make it to print. A letter from 26 October 1976 from Vătășianu's private archive published very late, in 2002⁴², was written to the secretary of the Central Committee of the Romanian Communist Party, Cornel Burtică. After having exhausted his arguments in the few places where he could express his viewpoints (during the meetings held at the Academy, for example) and in the absence of the alternative to publish his views uncensored, Vătășianu chose this approach of expressing his views on what he regarded not as isolated ideas, but as an entire movement in which "Romanian art" contained all artistic manifestations in the Romanian territories, no matter their age or authors. The direct criticism of Vatasianu's stance began with an article published in the *Scântea* newspaper⁴³ on 14 April 1976, written by the ethnographer Tancred Bănățeanu, entitled "Arta populară a tuturor regiunilor țării, componentă a epopeii noastre naționale" [The Folk Art of All Regions of the Country, as Part of our National Epopee], in which the author wrote about the "unity through diversity" of folk art; he continued in a project proposed at the Academy for Political and Social Sciences regarding a treatise on "Istoria artelor plastice românești" [The History of Romanian Fine Arts]:

"During the meeting held for discussing the project I have raised an objection to the title, because we cannot speak of Romanian fine art from the periods that precede the formation of the Romanian people by thousands of years, periods during which migrations took place. If the inclusion of the prehistoric period in a history of Romanian art did not raise scientific objections (unflattering for the authors), the inclusion of the current countrymen in the notion of 'Romanian art' would seem not only scientifically absurd, but also a chauvinistic act, directly contradicting the political principles so clearly expressed in the laws of this country, in the President of the R.S.R.'s speeches, as well as in reality (in schools, in cultural institutions, theatre, opera, etc.), all created and financed by our State. The fact that in our country, in our common past, there have been close contacts between cohabiting people and that convergent aspirations were formed is debatable, but not so far as to assess a national union. Comrade President Nicolae Ceaușescu himself has also expressed this opinion quite clearly, especially in his speeches regarding the necessity of maintaining and respecting the national states. As a matter of fact, an inclusion of all artistic manifestations in Romania into a single entity is in contradiction with the

incontestable evidence of the existence of a Romanian elite art that has particularities that are clearly different from the art of the cohabitants. The title of a treatise on art history that is unrestricted by chronological expansion and that includes migrations and ethnic cohabitations for diverse periods of time must show that it will approach not only exclusively Romanian art, but also the artistic evolution that had taken place in different circumstances in the territory, which was absolutely dominated by the Romanian people from the beginning of the Middle Ages"⁴⁴.

During the same meeting of the Academy, it was decided that the treatise needed to include in its introductory chapter an explanation regarding the inclusion of the art of minority groups in Romania into the concept of "Romanian art", thus following the model provided by Vasile Drăguț's *Dicționar enciclopedic de artă medievală românească*, which Vătășianu also sanctions:

"Any explanation is nothing but a sophism which not even the author believes and which cannot be credited; in reality, a book such as this Encyclopaedic dictionary is nothing more than an argument in the hands of our enemies; through the title of the book that is easily translatable and easy to understand by any foreigner and through the first illustration in the book (the Evangelical church from Cisnădioara, followed by countless other illustrations like the ones showing the Roman-Catholic church from Alba-Iulia, the Black Church from Brasov, etc.), our enemies can prove that the R.S.R. tolerates such unspeakable manifestations of chauvinism. For the foreigner, after he reads the title and compares it to some of the images, he will obviously not waste any more time reading or asking for a translation of the 'Foreword' in which the author offers (on page 8) a naïve excuse as justification for the inclusion of the 'works of Saxons, Szeklers, Hungarians, Serbians and other nationalities' into the category of Romanian art"⁴⁵.

Actually, what Vătășianu was trying to amend, even using references to Nicolae Ceaușescu⁴⁶, was the discourse of uniformization constantly evolving since the 1960s just to project, obsessively and aberrantly, a national idea over all of Romanian history. In a state where the powers wanted a homogeneous socialist society, there was not much

42 Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 210–212.

43 The official daily newspaper of the Romanian Communists.

44 Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 187–188.

45 *Ibidem*, p. 188.

46 In official relations references to the speeches of Nicolae Ceaușescu were obligatory in the age.

14/ Ceiling painting, Orthodox Monastery in Humor, Suceava County, Moldavia, 16th century

room for a discourse on particular values and cultural diversity. Fueled by the agenda of the nineteenth and the early twentieth century, the myth of the “unity” of Romanians from times immemorial (hand in hand with other myths, such as their continuity on the “Carpathian-Danubian-Pontic” land, the fight for independence, etc.) has become, like in any totalitarian state, a major thesis of a propagandistic discourse of internal and external legitimization⁴⁷.

The period between 1965 and 1970, which historians perceived as (comparatively) ideologically relaxed and relatively more open to dialogue (along with simplifying the procedures of travel abroad, dynamizing cultural and scientific exchange with the West, rehabilitating some of the subjects of national history and some of the

previously censured historians, and also more discreetly controlling publications, etc.), was followed again by major interference from the those in power, now Nicolae Ceausescu⁴⁸. In his speeches, culture had to be militant, placed at the service of the construction of socialism. It was meant to educate the masses, contribute to the forging of the “new man”, therefore it had to abandon its elitist attitude and publish works of popularization, conferences, exhibitions and shows for laborers. Then, from the initial interest in the history of the masses and the Communist Party, Ceausescu gradually moved on to the celebration of more and more historical events (his interest in Transylvania and the Union of 1918 started around 1968), his association with symbols of national history, which he wanted to appear as ancient and great as

possible, even at the cost of falsifying data. Many new graduates of the “Stefan Gheorghiu” Party School were placed in key positions in research and at the universities, unscrupulously serving the new directives of the ruling party. Professional historians could only keep their positions at the university, apply for doctorates, or have any kind of position of leadership if they had “clean” political “files”, were members of the Communist Party, and had an “ideological and propaganda activity” in favor of the only Party and its leader⁴⁹. Following a plan coordinated by the Central Committee of the Communist Party, the Academy of Social and Political Sciences (ASSP) was founded in 1970, an institution meant to coordinate and ideologically control research in the social and political sciences, most importantly for the official propaganda of the Communist party-state. Beginning in October 1972, ASSP had to “approve synthetic works with political-ideological subjects”, and an editorial board was created for this purpose in the following year⁵⁰.

During his visit to Asia (China, South Korea and Vietnam) in 1971, Ceausescu discovered new forms of personal cult and propaganda through culture. On his return, at the meeting of the Central Committee of the Party, he presented the so-called “July Theses”, intended as the beginning of a “cultural mini-revolution” in Romania. In fact, this meant the start of the country’s re-Stalinization, a brutal ideological intervention in all fields of life. Freedom of speech was drastically reduced in a very short time, prohibiting the publication, at home or abroad, of any material that might have prejudiced the state. To control all this, the Council of Social Culture and Education (CCES) was founded. Culture was again isolated from the outside, and inside, it was invaded by texts feeding on Ceausescu’s speeches and especially the theses of 1971⁵¹. Then there were others as well: the most important of these were *Programul multilateral pcr de făurire a societății* [The Multilateral Program of the PCR of Forging Society] delivered at the PCR Congress of 1974 and the *Programul cultural adoptat de Congresul Culturii și Educației Socialiste* [The Cultural Program Adopted by the Congress of Socialist Culture and Education] from 1976, where Ceausescu was no longer contented

with giving partial indications on how history should be written, but outlined all its directions. The works published had to prove the continuity and unity of the Romanian people and their worldwide importance, heroic past, all of which also carried xenophobic messages. Protochronism, with its tendency to discover “Romanian” heritage and values in the very distant past, before other peoples, started to ravage Romanian historiography as well⁵².

The state’s attempts to create means for propaganda with the help of historians by interfering with the scholarly criteria of research determined the production of great synthetic works with large teams of authors, necessarily containing also party

47 Katherine Verdery, *Compromis și rezistență. Cultura română sub Ceausescu* [Compromise and Resistance. Romanian Culture under Ceausescu], Bucharest 1994, pp. 76 ff.; Lucian Boia, “De la postcomunism la postnaționalism” [From Postcommunism to Postnationalism], *Xenopoliana*, 11/1–4 (1994), p. 124; Zub, *Orizont* (n. 1), pp. 80–82, p. 115; Dragoman Oanță-Marghitu, *Arheologie* (n. 1), p. 20.

48 In the years from 1965 to 1970 there was a period of consolidation of power. The Declaration of April 1964 publicly announced the separation from the Soviet Union, grounding the political legitimacy of the Romanian Communist Party which played as the defender of national values in the society. On 19 March 1965, Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej died, and his successor, Nicolae Ceausescu, was appointed first general secretary of the RCP, then in 1967 president of the State Council, cumulating all the supreme offices of power. In 1974 he became President of the Socialist Republic of Romania. After his speech on 21 August 1968, condemning the invasion of Czechoslovakia, in an atmosphere of apparent liberalization, many intellectuals were tempted to join the Romanian Communist Party. Vlad Georgescu, *Politică și istorie. Cazul comuniștilor români. 1944–1977* [Politics and History: The Case of Romanian Communists, 1944–1977], *Postfață* [Afterwords] by Radu Popa, Bucharest 1991; Verdery, *Compromis* (n. 46), pp. 82–85; Marian Petcu, *Puterea și cultura. O istorie a cenzurii* [Power and Culture. A History of Censorship], Iași 1999, p. 176; Moisa, *Istorie* (n. 16), pp. 54–62.

49 See the fourth chapter entitled *Culturii și noile mituri (1971–1977)* [False Men of Culture and the New Myths (1971–1977)], in Georgescu, *Politică* (n. 47); Verdery, *Compromis* (n. 46), pp. 97 ff.; Petcu, *Puterea* (n. 47), p. 177; Zub, *Orizont* (n. 1), pp. 109–112.

50 At the time of its establishment, it had 220 members (associates and tenured members). It also had a Department of Theory and History of Art and Literature, which included Virgil Vătășianu. A certain number of research institutes from Bucharest and from the entire country had then become its subordinates. Ștefan Bosomitu: “La 19 februarie 1970 s-a întrunit Adunarea generală de constituire a Academiei de Științe Sociale și Politice a R.S.R.” [On 19 February 1970, the General Assembly Formed to Establish the Academy of Political and Social Sciences of the R.P.R.], in [http://www.iicr.ro/la-19-februarie-1970-s-a-intrunit-adunarea-general-a-de-constituirea-academiei-de-stiinta-sociale-si-politice-a-r-s-r], last accessed on 20.08.2016]; Cosmin Popa, “Asaltul regimului Ceausescu împotriva Academiei RSR” [The Assault of the Ceausescu Regime against the Academy of the RSR], *Revista Bibliotecii Academiei Române*, 1/1 (2016), pp. 113–124.

51 Cristina Petrescu, Dragoș Petrescu, “Restalinizarea vieții culturale românești, Tezele din iulie 1971” [The Re-Stalinization of Romanian Cultural Life. The July Theses 1971], *Arhiva Cotidianului*, x (53), 1996, pp. 1–3. About the way he viewed writing history: Georgescu, *Politică* (n. 46), p. 64–65.

52 Verdery, *Compromis* (n. 46), pp. 152 ff.; Boia, *Istorie și mit* (n. 1), p. 59 ff.; Moisa, *Istorie* (n. 16), p. 136 ff.

15/ Portal of the Lutheran clergy house, coat-of-arms with inscription in Sibiu (Hermannstadt, Nagyszeben), Sibiu County, Transylvania, 1502

activists. The entire period of the regime was supported by such great projects which had to be published for festive events. In 1975–1976, a longer list of such syntheses were ordered: a treatise on the military history of the Romanian people, and a national history of 10 volumes⁵³. The first one was published in six volumes between 1984–1989. The first two volumes of the second reached typography, but in the end were not published because of a disagreement between the professional authors (among the dozens of authors selected by non-scientific criteria) and the chief editor⁵⁴.

As revealed by the letter of Vătășianu previously mentioned, there was also a commission for a *Istoria artei plastice românești* [A History of Romanian Fine Arts]. But the history of Romanian fine arts from the Paleolithic to the present was also not published in the form conceived by the ASSP. Before the fall of the regime, only a history of Romanian architecture had been published⁵⁵ and the two above-mentioned volumes of *Arta românească* of Vasile Drăguț (I) and Vasile Florea (II). However, a general introduction to art monuments was published much later at Leipzig. Written by Vătășianu, it bore the title *Kunstdenkmäler in Rumänien*⁵⁶. It was published ten years after the contract was signed, and it was never permitted to be translated into Romanian, as was originally intended. Its censoring might have been due to the fact that it covered monuments included in Ceausescu's demolition plans executed after the 1977 earthquake⁵⁷.

Many of the art history works during the Ceausescu regime were published by the publishing house of the Romanian Academy RPR, later RSR, *Editura Științifică și Enciclopedică* and the Meridiane publishing house. The latter had commissioned a special series of books on art and civilization. Publications on the history of architecture were usually published by the *Editura Tehnică*. The synthetic works mentioned before were also published by the first two publishers. Some of the art historians were on the editorial board of the Meridiane (e.g., Vasile Drăguț, after 1965), or even headed the publishing house (such as Ion Frunzetti in 1971–1972). What's more, Vasile Florea continued his activity at Meridiane after 1989. We are not yet fully aware of their influence in these

editorial offices, but it must be kept in mind that, before its dissolution in 1977, the GDPP, or, since 1975, *Comitetul pentru Presă și Tipărituri* (Committee for Press and Publications), which had the *Serviciul Ideologie* (Ideology Service) in its subordination, also controlled the publishing houses publishing art history. Moreover, censorship abounded after 1977, and a part of it was exercised by the publishers⁵⁸. They had to face not only ideological pressure, but also some rules of self-financing decreed in 1978⁵⁹. The material conditions, ideological pressure, censorship and self-censorship placed publishers, research institutions, authors and their books into various special situations, which we are only gradually learning about, with the help of archives, testimonies and investigations that have already started in other fields, including history. As Katherine Verdery has already signaled, some of the aspects help our outline. As control was polycentric and there were many institutions dealing with history, from universities to research units administratively working under competing superior organizations, there was a certain amount of chaos in the system, which could be taken advantage of. Verdery also speaks about the centrifugal tendencies of the centers from Iași and Cluj, where local historians considered themselves more competent to write about Moldavia and Transylvania than historians from Bucharest. However, general comprehensive works were organized in Bucharest, the center of decision and influence, and historians from there tended to impose interpretations even within fields they had not studied, to the same degree as historians from Iași or Cluj, and were not trained enough to understand all regional specificities or did not have access to all of the information⁶⁰. Disagreements and tension were also perceivable in the case of art historians from Cluj and Bucharest⁶¹, even if Vătășianu, a historian from Cluj, was called to take care of the chapters on Transylvanian art in history or art history works ordered by Bucharest⁶².

In the period from 1982 to 1989, no more syntheses, encompassing all the historical provinces of Romania, were published under the title of "Romanian art" or "Romanian architecture"⁶³, but they did return after the regime change in 1989. Disciples, former colleagues and collaborators of the

authors who had already died re-published the *Istoria artei feudale în Țările Române* [unchanged edition] by Virgil Vătășianu⁶⁴, the *Dicționarul enciclopedic de artă medievală românească*⁶⁵ and Vasile Drăguț's 1982 *Arta românească*⁶⁶. Vasile Florea returned on his own to the project of a popularization work, publishing the *Istoria artei românești. I. Arta veche și medievală* [The History of Romanian Art. I. Ancient and Medieval Art] in 1991, the part that Drăguț had initially dealt with. Cristian Moisescu published a volume of medieval architecture which he intended to be scientific, entitled *Arhitectura*

53 Georgescu, *Politică* (n. 47), pp. 101–106. Before the treatise was ordered, a brochure of 65 pages was written and sent to institutions across the country by ASSP as a guide for historians to know how to write the "real" history.

54 Radu Popa, *Postfață*, in Georgescu, *Politică* (n. 47), pp. 140–141. Unfortunately, the project which had repeatedly failed before was restarted by the initiative of the Romanian Academy in 1995, but it has proved once more to become a highly criticizable endeavor. See on this: Daniel Ursprung, "Historiographie im Zeichen der Beharrung. Kritische Anmerkungen zur umfangreichsten Gesamtdarstellung der rumänischen Geschichte", in *Südost-Forschungen*, LXIII–LXIV (2004–2005), pp. 408–421; Șerban Papacostea, "Tratatul academic Istoria Românilor. O percepție străină" [The Academic Treatise The History of the Romanians. A Foreign Perception], *Revista 22*, 10. 08. 2007, [http://revista22.ro/3943/.html, last accessed on 22. 09. 2016]. At the original commission in 1976, Vătășianu was appointed to write the parts on medieval art in volumes II and III. Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), p. 144.

55 Gheorghe Curinschi-Vorona, *Istoria arhitecturii în România* [History of Architecture in Romania], Bucharest 1981. It is collective work in fact, but the authors are not listed on the cover, only at the beginning of the book.

56 *Kunstdenkmäler in Rumänien; ein Bildhandbuch*, Leipzig 1986.

57 Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), p. 138. After the 1977 earthquake which affected parts of Romania, Ceausescu ordered an extensive systematization plan of Bucharest, to which historical monuments also fell victim, some being demolished, others moved.

58 Verdery, *Compromis* (n. 46), pp. 169, 213, 230–232; Corobca, *Controlul* (n. 13), p. 112; Zainea, "Direcția" (n. 13), p. 162. The dissolution of the GDPP did not mean the abolition of censorship, as some of the censors were transferred to editorial offices of newspapers and magazines, publishing houses, ministries, higher education institutions, other public institutions, and any organization which transmitted information. Above all these, at the top, was censorship directed by the Party, by Ceausescu and his wife. This control and censorship was also doubled by self-censorship. Corobca, *Controlul* (n. 13), pp. 297 ff.

59 Verdery, *Compromis* (n. 46), pp. 94–96.

60 *Ibidem*, pp. 213, 336, n. 11.

61 On art history education in both centers, see Teacă, "In Search" (n. 3), pp. 451–460; Nicolae Sabău, Corina Simon, Vlad Țoca, *Istoria artei la Universitatea din Cluj* [Art History at the University of Cluj], Nicolae Sabău ed., vol. I (1919–1987), Cluj-Napoca 2010.

62 Tensions existed primarily with George Oprescu (Simion, *Artă* [n. 3], pp. 100–111) and Vasile Drăguț.

63 Virgil Vătășianu's volume only contained various studies on art history in the historical provinces of Romania, under the title: *Studii de artă veche românească și universală* [Studies in Romanian and Universal Old Art], Bucharest 1987, published by Meridiane.

64 Preface by, edited by Marius Porumb, Cluj-Napoca 2001.

65 Edited by Tereza Sinigalia, Bucharest 2000.

66 Vasile Drăguț, *Arta românească. Preistorie. Antichitate. Ev Mediu. Renaștere. Baroc* [Romanian Art. Prehistory. Antiquity. Middle Ages. Renaissance. Baroque], preface by Cristian Moisescu, Bucharest 2000.

românească veche [Old Romanian Architecture]⁶⁷. Ioan Godea published *Arhitectura la români. De la obârșii la Cozia* [Romanian Architecture. From the Origins to Cozia], a work starting in fact with Dacian architecture and passing to Transylvanian Romanesque and Gothic, finally reaching Cozia in Wallachia⁶⁸. Vasile Florea, probably at the request of the publishing house, also republished the *Istoria artei românești*⁶⁹ several times, continued with *Arta românească de la origini până în prezent* [Romanian Art from the Origins to the Present] in 2016⁷⁰. Each of these works is indebted to a lesser or greater extent to the manner of addressing extensive subjects on the territory of Romania (in Vasile Florea's case, also the Republic of Moldova), sometimes based on the same structure as Vasile Drăguț. They all look for the "origins", ethnically levelled and made uniform, they present art and architecture as phenomena which are necessarily in evolution (despite white spots in the data, the variety of stylistic influences, discontinuations and belatedness, etc.), in language and concepts that were outdated and never sufficiently critically filtered after the pollution of the Protochronism of the 1980s–1990s, demonstrating thus that the distortions of the age were far from being perceived as such. Older criticisms on "Romanian art" such as Vătășianu's were unheard of in Ceausescu's time, but apparently not even after the monograph dedicated to him appeared in 2002, to which the documents referenced here were annexed⁷¹.

These extensions of the nationalist discourse and Protochronism into the present are due to

some nostalgic authors, but also to the commercial appetite of certain publishing houses who still lack any professional reviewers, but seem to have intuited the needs of the audience, including young students in art history and architectural history. Paradoxically, these are published simultaneously with a history of literature, which is critical of the myths of Communism (also partly still maintained by publishers' marketing), but which has neglected art history as yet.

Beyond the new interests and tendencies listed here, art historiography should recognize its past contribution to a politically manipulated history, it should ideologically clear out its content, reconsider its methodology of research and writing, re-analyze a huge amount of new data partly brought in by other disciplines (such as archaeology and anthropology), it should be open to obscured subjects, it should step beyond the linguistic barriers which led to the development of parallel historiographies, and discover and emphasize the artistic (along with linguistic, confessional, social) diversity of regions [Figs 1–15], while detaching itself from the perspective of the nation-state that is anachronistic for medieval art and architecture.

Translated by Anca Chiorean and Emese Czintos

⁶⁷ Bucharest 2001.

⁶⁸ Oradea 2007. The book is highly illustrative of many distortions and confusions of the previous historiography. Reviewed by Ioan Augustin, [http://atelier.liternet.ro/articol/11273/Augustin-Ioan/Arhitectura-la-romani.html, last accessed on 22. 09. 2016].

⁶⁹ Bucharest 2007, 2009.

⁷⁰ Bucharest 2016.

⁷¹ Simion, *Artă* (n. 3), pp. 141–194.

summary

Koncepty zkreslené ideologií

Pohled na středověké „rumunské“ umění (1945–1989)

Historiografie středověkého umění v Rumunsku nevykazuje dostatečné množství sebereflexe nad svojí rolí v diskurzu o národní identitě mezi lety 1945 až 1989, kdy byla země ovládána totalitárním režimem. Záměrem článku Ileany Burnichioiu je tudíž otevření cesty k širší analýze tohoto problému. Prostřednictvím rozboru konceptů „rumunského umění“ a „rumunské architektury“ autorka usiluje o odhalení jistých vodítek sloužících k uchopení dějin středověkého umění a architektury utvářených pod tlakem vládnoucí ideologie.

I v dnešní době se zmíněné pojmy často objevují jak v akademické, tak také v populární literatuře publikované po roce 1989, a to i přesto, že nezřídka zahrnují rovněž umění a architekturu jiných etnických skupin a pokrývají velmi rozsáhlá časová období. Takovéto standardizující koncepty jsou dnes součástí všeobecného slovníku, ačkoli zároveň mohou stát u zrodu nejasností. Rumunsko je státem, jehož hranice se až do roku 1940 soustavně proměňovaly – tedy státem ustanoveným z mnoha etnicky, nábožensky a kulturně rozdílných historických provincií s bohatými a mnohovrstevnatými

dějiny, sahajícími od prehistorie až k moderní době, kdy byly tyto jednotky politicky sjednoceny.

Autorka zkoumá dané koncepty užívané autory a díly publikovanými vydavatelstvími s vyšším renomé v národním měřítku v průběhu vlády komunistického režimu a dále od roku 1989. Tato analýza odhaluje snahu kodifikovat pojmy „rumunské středověké umění“ nebo „rumunská středověká architektura“ pro celé území rumunského státu, a to především kolem roku 1965. Odborná pojednání, syntézy a další texty užívající koncept „rumunského umění“ jsou sledovány chronologicky v dialogu s politickým kontextem zahrnujícím oficiální postoje a názory spjaté s kulturními a historickými spisy. Autorka tento rozbor navíc doplňuje o množství dokumentů pocházejících ze soukromých archivů. Tímto způsobem vyplouvají na povrch rozmanité snahy vybraných historiků umění (jako byl např. Vasile Drăguț z Bukurešti) a vydavatelství o propagování historických mýtů sloužících režimu (jako právě mýtus o jednotě Rumunska), stejně jako kritický přístup některých osobností (jako v případě Virgila Vătășianu z Kluže) vůči vládnoucí ideologii.